

CORPUS LINGUISTICS AS A NEW FIELD

Sahila Baghir Mustafayeva

Doctor of Philosophy in Philology, Associate Professor Azerbaijan, Baku Azerbaijan University
of Languages

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Abstract. *The article deals with the corpus linguistics in linguistics. The article analyzes the corpus linguistics as there is some rapid tendency towards using this kind of linguistics. The definition on the corpus linguistics given by various linguists has been analyzed in the article. The article reveals the key points of this kind of linguistics that distinguishes it from other ones. Besides, the article highlights the corpus linguistics as a science that uses computer resources to analyze and understand patterns and variants in language. Corpus linguistics turns out to be leading to the development of new linguistic theories. The corpus linguistics is sure to be a new branch of linguistics, so it has the novelty in its branch. It is observed to be developing day by day, therefore it covers relevance.*

Key words: *corpus, linguistics, linguist, field, computer, resource*

Ключевые слова: *корпус, лингвистика, лингвист, область, компьютер, ресурс*

Açar sözlər: *korpus, dilçilik, dilçi, sahə, kompüter, mənbə*

INTRODUCTION

Corpus linguistics is a science that uses computer resources to analyze and understand patterns and variations in language, leading to the development of new theories of language. It allows translators, language learners, and linguists to conduct sophisticated research using web-based corpus research.

Corpus linguistics is a relatively new and rapidly changing field. As computer resources, especially web-based resources, have developed, sophisticated corpus studies have become increasingly useful to translators, language learners, or linguists. Our understanding of how language varieties differ from one another and our appreciation of the ways in which words are formed in language have been immeasurably improved by corpus studies, and new theories of language have developed that take corpus research as a starting point.

Corpus linguistics is not a descriptive theory of language, but rather a set of methodologies. It (corpus linguistics) essentially involves:

- 1) Examining naturally occurring language;
- 2) Examining relatively large numbers of such languages;
- 3) Observing relative frequencies, both in raw form and through statistical operations;
- 4) Observing patterns of association between text types or between groups of words (8).

In this way, the theory of corpus linguistics may seem simple, but the practice of engaging in corpus linguistics is not at all ordinary, since each researcher must be able to determine what is meant by a “feature” and what frequencies should be observed.

Approaches to the use of corpuses that rely on the existence of categories derived from non-corpus studies of language are sometimes called “corpus-based” approaches (Tognini-Bonelli, 2001).

Discussions:

Corpus linguistics research can be compared to, but cannot fully encompass, hypotheses derived from grammatical descriptions based on intuition or limited data (Aarts, 1993). Corpus

studies are based on a broader range of data. For example, D. Biber et al. describe work on ellipsis from a typological and psycholinguistic perspective, which predicts that one of the three possible clause positions for ellipsis in American spoken English is more frequent than the others (Biber, 1998). Corpus research shows that this is accurate information. D. Biber et al. comment that “corpus-based analysis of grammatical structure can reveal features that were never suspected before” (Biber, 1998). They include as examples the surprisingly high frequency of complex relative clause constructions in speech, and the frequency of simplified grammatical constructions in academic prose.

A clearer integration between linguistic theory and corpus linguistics is demonstrated by Matthias’s work on presupposition. Corpus studies show that this work draws its categories from the existing description of the English language (Kennedy, 1998). Corpus research is an integral part of theory because it shows that statements about the probability of occurrence of each item are the only way.

However, certain radical problems can also be found in the description of language. J. Sinclair argues that the information observable in the corpus (and nowhere else) involves descriptions that are significantly different from those generally available (Sinclair, 2001). Both the descriptions and the theories they in turn form are, in E. Tognini-Bonellini’s term, “corpus-driven” (Tognini-Bonelli, 2001).

Some of the difficulties with corpus-based theories are:

- 1) Lexis and grammar are not distinct, and grammar is not an abstract system underlying language;
- 2) Any kind of choice is strictly limited by lexical choice;
- 3) Meaning is not atomistic, but exists in words, is prosodic, belongs to variable meaning units, and is always present in texts.

The concept of pattern grammar focuses on how different lexical items behave differently depending on how they are completed. Without describing that individual lexical behavior, grammatical generalizations about completion cannot be made. Similarly, the choice between features such as “positive” and “negative” depends to some extent on the lexical item, since some verbs are negated more often than others. In other words, the probability of occurrence of any grammatical category is strongly influenced not only by the environment but also by the lexicon used.

J. Sinclair suggests, for example, that meaning can be attributed to “units of meaning”. J. Sinclair describes language according to the “principle of open choice” (Sinclair, 2001). In this case, the speaker chooses the semantic prosody and the main word, and the rest occurs without choice.

Another theoretical approach to the non-randomness of language in practice is T. McEnergy’s theory of “lexical justification” (McEnergy, 2001). He notes that it is possible for certain words to have a greater (or less) frequency at the beginning of paragraphs or texts or in lexical chains than would be predicted by random distribution, and he calls this “textual colligativeness”: this includes: the individual’s experience with words in context over many years, the use of each lexical item in a particular word combination or colligative configuration, or the selection of each lexical item to play a certain role in the text, etc. This theory is successfully implemented in grammar and discourse. It cannot be said that a word or expression necessarily belongs to a particular class, but rather a word or expression is prepared to be used according to the norms of different categories (Mustafayeva, 2024).

F. Reppen sees the study of meaning as the main task of corpus linguistics, because the corpus is a form of language that functions as a social act, that is, it is not a psychological phenomenon, but a social phenomenon. In corpus linguistics, meaning is considered as a “social phenomenon” (Meyer, 2002). On the other hand, meaning is not shared in an abstract form: different individuals mean different things even when they use the same lexical item. More precisely, F. Reppen claims that meaning is social, because the meaning of a word or expression lies in the sum of the ways in which that word or expression is used. He quotes the word school (Meyer, 2002). The word school can be used in different contexts, and in each of these contexts the word contributes something slightly different to the meaning of the discourse as a whole (for example, after school, having a hard time at school, school holidays, high school, medical school, skipping school, walking to school, etc.). What we might think of as the “dictionary” meaning of school is a generalization of all these examples, but each example is realized somewhat differently from this generalization. To see what a word or phrase means, or what it meant at any given time in history, we would have to examine every instance of the word. This is impossible, but a corpus offers us many examples, and the Internet, as a collection of texts, gives us even more.

Conclusions:

Linguists also use computers to store/retrieve written or spoken samples of human language. These can then be used by lexicographers to write dictionaries, and syntax experts to write grammar books.

Corpus linguistics approaches the study of language in use through a corpus. A corpus is a large, principled collection of naturally occurring language samples that are stored electronically.

Corpus linguistics answers two important questions: 1) what specific samples are associated with lexical or grammatical features?; 2) how are these samples differentiated within variants?

A text corpus is a very large collection of text produced by real users of a language and used to analyze how words, phrases, and language are used in general, and is used by linguists, lexicographers, social scientists, humanities, natural language processing specialists, and many other fields. Corpora are also used to create various language databases used in software development, such as predictive keyboards, spell checkers, grammar correction, text/speech understanding systems, text-to-speech modules, machine translation systems, and many others.

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